

“Do-support” is kinda dumb. A reanalysis of English auxiliary structures

What is “do-support”?

In English, questions involve the movement of an “auxiliary”, while negative statements involve the addition of “not” to an auxiliary:

Tom **will** eat chips.

Will Tom eat chips?

Tom **will** not eat chips.

Tom **should** eat chips.

Should Tom eat chips?

Tom **should** not eat chips.

However, in sentences like the following, the traditional analysis is that an auxiliary is “inserted” in questions and negative statements because these statements lack such an auxiliary and so need to be “supported” – hence “do-support” (and/or “did-support”):

Tom eats chips. (no auxiliary)

Does Tom eat chips? (inserted auxiliary)

Tom **does** not eat chips. (inserted auxiliary)

Tom ate chips. (no auxiliary)

Did Tom eat chips? (inserted auxiliary)

Tom **did** not eat chips. (inserted auxiliary)

Seems straightforward enough, right? So...

...why do we need to change a grammatical analysis if it works?

A grammatical analysis should be “maximally efficient” (Chomsky, 1993). Such a system “must do with as few levels of representation operations, and technical devices as possible” (Hicks, 2009). For example, if we have two analyses, A and B, and we find that A produces a correct utterance and B does not, then we can confidently say that we should adopt A as our analysis. However, if both A and B produce a correct utterance, then the choice between A and B depends on several other factors, including:

- Which analysis can be expressed in the simplest way
- Which analysis covers the most phenomena
- Which analysis requires the least number of additional analyses (so that if, for example, A was simpler than B but required a greater number of additional exceptions to pertain in all cases, then B might be a better choice, even if B was more complex than A; in other words, the principle of “Occam’s razor”)
- Which analysis best fits the wider analytical system we are using

What the choice should NOT be based on is:

- Which analysis conforms to what we have always done in the past

- Which analysis conforms to what everyone else is doing

If an analysis is rejected because it has never been proposed before or because no one else is publishing resources that use that analysis, then no progress would ever take place. So how does this apply to do-support? Well, I have developed an alternative, “maximally efficient” analysis that has significant advantages in terms of the wider analytical system we can use for English.

The current analysis. Yes, it’s crazy.

In linguistic theory (see Culicover, 2008, Ørsnes, 2011, Chung-hye Han and Anthony Kroch, no date, and Ecay, no date, for examples), do-support in English is explained by positing that auxiliaries occupy an “inflection” position above the verb phrase:

In questions, they then move to occupy a position above the clause:

When there is no auxiliary, the information that would otherwise be contained in the inflection position “drops” to inflect the verb:

In questions, there is no auxiliary to move to a position above the clause, therefore “do” is “inserted”:

Likewise, in negative statements, “not” somehow “blocks” the information that would otherwise be contained in the inflection position from dropping to inflect the verb. Again, there is no auxiliary to occupy the inflection position, therefore “do” is “inserted”

My analysis. Yes, it's clearer.

I propose that the simple present and simple past word forms already contain a "hidden" auxiliary; the word forms "eats" and "ate" are actually temporary replacements of "does eat" and "did eat" respectively:

Tom eats (= **does** eat) chips.

Does Tom eat chips?

Tom **does** not eat chips.

Tom ate (= **did** eat) chips.

Did Tom eat chips?

Tom **did** not eat chips.

The power of this analysis is that it allows us to posit that (1) ALL verb structures in English consist of an auxiliary plus a verb and (2) ALL verbs in English behave exactly the same way across all different structures. In other words, despite their frequency of use, ...

...the affirmative simple present and affirmative simple past are the exception rather than the rule:

positive statement	He will go.	He must go.	He can go.	He shall go.	He goes .
positive question	Will he go?	Must he go?	Can he go?	Shall he go?	Does he go?
negative statement	He will not go.	He must not go.	He cannot go.	He shall not go.	He does not go.
negative question	Will he not go?	Must he not go?	Can he not go?	Shall he not go?	Does he not go?
emphasis	He WILL go.	He MUST go.	He CAN go.	He SHALL go.	He DOES go.
dropped verb	Yes, he will .	Yes, he must .	Yes, he can .	Yes, he shall .	Yes, he does .
adverb reversal	Never will he go.	Never must he go.	Never can he go.	Never shall he go.	Never does he go.
than-clause	I will go quicker than he will .	I must go quicker than he must .	I can go quicker than he can .	I shall go quicker than he shall .	I go quicker than he does .

positive statement	He would go.	He might go.	He could go.	He should go.	He went .
positive question	Would he go?	Might he go?	Could he go?	Should he go?	Did he go?
negative statement	He would not go.	He might not go.	He could not go.	He should not go.	He did not go.
negative question	Would he not go?	Might he not go?	Could he not go?	Should he not go?	Did he not go?
emphasis	He WOULD go.	He MIGHT go.	He COULD go.	He SHOULD go.	He DID go.
dropped verb	Yes, he would .	Yes, he might .	Yes, he could .	Yes, he should .	Yes, he did .
adverb reversal	Never would he go.	Never might he go.	Never could he go.	Never should he go.	Never did he go.
than-clause	I would go quicker than he would .	I might go quicker than he might .	I could go quicker than he could .	I should go quicker than he should .	I went quicker than he did .

This analysis is simply a logical expression of the idea of “logical form”/“deep structure” contrasting with “phonetic form”/“surface structure” (see, for example, Chomsky, 1976, Hornstein and Weinberg, 1990 and Fox, 2002, among others).

So what about “do” instead of “does”?

At first, it might not be apparent how this new, replacement-based analysis can account for the change from “does” to “do”:

Does Tom eat chips?

Do Tom and Jerry eat chips?

Eric **does** not go home.

Eric and Raj **do** not go home.

Traditional grammar posits that, because the auxiliary “do” inflects for number (“does” in the singular, “do” in the plural), it is a finite verb. However, there is a simpler analysis: “does” and “do” are *separate auxiliaries*. The auxiliary “does” is used with a singular subject and the auxiliary “do” is used with a plural subject. Here, the word forms “eat” and “go” are actually temporary replacements of “do eat” and “do go” respectively.

Tom eats (= **does** eat) chips.

Does Tom eat chips?

Tom **does** not eat chips.

Tom and Jerry eat (= **do** eat) chips.

Do Tom and Jerry eat chips?

Tom and Jerry **do** not eat chips.

positive statement	They will go.	They must go.	They can go.	They shall go.	They go.
positive question	Will they go?	Must they go?	Can they go?	Shall they go?	Do they go?
negative statement	They will not go.	They must not go.	They cannot go.	They shall not go.	They do not go.
negative question	Will they not go?	Must they not go?	Can they not go?	Shall they not go?	Do they not go?
emphasis	They WILL go.	They MUST go.	They CAN go.	They SHALL go.	They DO go.
dropped verb	Yes, they will .	Yes, they must .	Yes, they can .	Yes, they shall .	Yes, they do .
adverb reversal	Never will they go.	Never must they go.	Never can they go.	Never shall they go.	Never do they go.
than-clause	I will go quicker than they will .	I must go quicker than they must .	I can go quicker than they can .	I shall go quicker than they shall .	I go quicker than they do .

There is a precedent for this. Other auxiliaries were once analyzed in present/past pairs. We can analyze “does” and “did” as another – similarly symmetrical – addition to our list of auxiliaries:

can – could

does – did

may – might

shall – should

will – would

This analysis is no longer justified semantically or syntactically and all auxiliaries are considered equal. Nevertheless, in a similar way, “do” and “does” can be analyzed as separate, unchanging auxiliaries.

So what about the auxiliary verb “be”?

At first, it might also not be apparent how this new, replacement-based analysis can account for structures like the following with the verb “be”:

Tom **is** eating chips.

Is Tom eating chips?

Tom **is** not eating chips.

Tom **was** eating chips.

Was Tom eating chips?

Tom **was** not eating chips.

Traditional grammar posits that, here, “be” is being used as a finite “auxiliary verb”, just like “do” is considered a finite verb in do-support. Likewise, linguistic theory posits that, unlike lexical verbs, the verb “be” always “rises” to occupy the inflection position. Therefore, it can move to a position above the clause in questions and is not blocked by “not”:

However, there is a simpler analysis – there are still hypothetical underlying forms, namely “does be”, “do be” and “did be”:

Tom is (= **does** be) sad.

Tom and Jerry are (= **do** be) sad.

Tom was (= **did** be) sad.

The only difference is that “be” is *unbreakable*. In other words, “does be”, “do be” and “did be” are always replaced. Therefore, when movement occurs or “not” is added, the whole *replacement* moves and “not” is added to the whole replacement:

Tom **is** eating chips.
Is Tom eating chips?
 Tom **is** not eating chips.

Tom **was** eating chips.
Was Tom eating chips?
 Tom **was** not eating chips.

The only time “be” is ever broken is in negative imperatives and emphatic affirmative imperatives, which are themselves evidence of this underlying structure:

Do not be late!
Do be quiet!

So what about the auxiliary verb “have”?

This simple solution can also be applied to the verb “have”. Normally, “have” behaves just like any other verb:

Tom has (= **does** have) a cold.

Does Tom have a cold?

Tom **does** not have a cold.

Tom and Jerry have (= **do** have) a cold.

Do Tom and Jerry have a cold?

Tom and Jerry **do** not have a cold.

Tom had (= **did** have) a cold.

Did Tom have a cold?

Tom **did** not have a cold.

However, when it is followed by a past participle, it becomes like “be” – unbreakable:

Tom **has** gone.

*Tom **DOES** have gone.

Have Tom and Jerry gone?

*Do Tom and Jerry have gone?

Tom **had** not gone.

*Tom did not have gone.

What about participles? Aren't they kinda like verbs?

This analysis has an important implication on the status of participles. If all verbs can be analyzed as above, there is no need to analyze “do”, “have” and “be” as finite auxiliary verbs. In other words, “does”, “do” and “did” are posited auxiliaries in their own right, while “be” and “have” are full verbs in their own right that are (only sometimes, in the case of “have”) unbreakable. We can therefore posit present and past participles as simply created adjectives – just like any other adjective – and NOT forms of verbs. As a result, the structure of clauses with participles in English can be completely reanalyzed as consistently containing a single verb, not two:

Tom is (= does be) sick. (verb + adjective complement)

Tom is (= does be) going. (verb + adjective complement)

Eric was (= did be) tall. (verb + adjective complement)

Eric was (= did be) taken. (verb + adjective complement)

Replacements are powerful. Really.

Another advantage of this replacement-based analysis is that the process of replacement itself can explain other grammatical phenomena in English, including comparative and superlative adjectives, pronouns and adverbs:

Tom feels happier (= more happy).

Tom was the tallest (= most tall).

Tom saw his mother. He saw her (= his mother).

Where (= to what place) are you going?

I play football occasionally (= on some occasions).

We do not posit that comparative adjectives that cannot take the "...er" suffix undergo some form of "more-support" or that superlative adjectives that cannot take the "...est" suffix undergo some form of "most-support". An analysis that posits comparative and superlative forms as replacements for an underlying "more" and "most", however, is directly parallel with an underlying "does", "do" and "did":

Eric eats (= **does** eat).

Eric looks happier (= **more** happy).

Suzie purred (= **did** purr).

Suzie was the prettiest (= **most** pretty) cat ever.

He looked young before but now he looks even younger (= **more** young).

He looked young before but now he looks even **MORE** young.

Likewise, the idea of "unbreakable" replacements has a direct parallel in the underlying forms of "better", "best", "worse" and "worst" being the logical-but-unspoken "more good", "most good", "more bad" and "most bad":

Eric IS (= does be) here.

*Eric DOES be here. (unbreakable)

Eric is our BEST (=most good) cook.

*Eric is our MOST good cook. (unbreakable)

In fact, the idea of replacements may allow us to dispense with the problematic category of "adverbs" in English altogether (in that they are just replacements for prepositional phrases):

softly (= in a soft manner)

then (= at that time)

here (= in this place)

Interested?

If you found this analysis of do-support in English interesting, you should check out my book: English Grammar: A Comprehensive Guide. This pedagogical grammar uses both the idea of replacements and other neat little analyses for English – so take a look! (Yes, this is a shameless plug.)

References

Aaron Ecay, no date, *Investigating the history of English do-support using automatically annotated corpora* <aaronecay.com/files/Ecay-do-corpora-poster.pdf>

Bjarne Ørnsnes, 2011, *Non-finite do-support in Danish*, *Empirical Issues in Syntax and Semantics*, 8, 409–434

Chung-hye Han and Anthony Kroch, no date, *The rise of do-support in English: Implications for clause structure*, <[ftp://babel.ling.upenn.edu/facpapers/tony_kroch/papers/nels30.pdf](http://babel.ling.upenn.edu/facpapers/tony_kroch/papers/nels30.pdf)>

Danny Fox, 2002, *On logical form*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Glyn Hicks, 2009, *The derivation of anaphoric relations*, *Linguistics Today*

Noam Chomsky, 1976, *Conditions on rules of grammar*, *Linguistic Analysis*, 2, 303–351

Noam Chomsky, 1993, *A minimalist program for linguistic theory*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology Occasional Papers in Linguistics, 1

Norbert Hornstein and Amy Weinberg, 1990, *The necessity of LF*, *The Linguistic Review*, 7, 129–168

Peter W. Culicover, 2008, *The rise and fall of constructions and the history of English do-support*, *Journal of Germanic Linguistics*, 20.1, 1–52

All syntax trees were created using Miles Shang's tree generator.